

Synthesis of some New 8-Methoxy-5-substituted-amino-methylcoumarins as Possible Antibacterial Agents

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A number of 8-methoxy-5-substituted-coumarins have been synthesised by chloromethylation of 8-methoxycoumarin and subsequent condensation of the chloromethyl compound with various amines. Their structures were established by analytical data and spectral studies. Some of the compounds were found active against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*.

BENZO- α -pyrones are naturally occurring and possess wide spectrum of physiological activities¹. Literature survey has revealed that groups like dimethoxy², aminomethyl³, halogens⁴ and heterocyclic moieties⁵ enhance antibacterial activities. It was therefore thought of interest to synthesise 8-methoxy-5-substituted-aminomethylcoumarin derivatives of the type 3 and evaluate their antibacterial activities.

8-Methoxy-5-chloromethylcoumarin⁶ (2) was prepared by passing dry HCl in a mixture of 8-methoxycoumarin dissolved in glacial acetic acid, paraformaldehyde and ZnCl₂. This on condensation with various simple and substituted aliphatic, aromatic and heterocyclic primary and secondary amines in absolute ethanol furnished the corresponding 8-methoxy-5-substituted-aminomethylcoumarin (3) and structures of the compounds have been established by elemental analysis and spectral data (Table 1).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Microanalysis of compounds were performed on a Coleman instrument. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 408 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested through tlc.

8-Methoxy-5-anilinomethylcoumarin (3a). 8-Methoxy-5-chloromethylcoumarin (2; 1 g) was refluxed with aniline (0.5 g) in absolute ethanol on a water-bath for 4 h. Alcohol was then removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was scrubbed with petroleum ether and recrystallised from alcohol as yellowish shining crystals (65%), m.p. 190°. The compounds 3c, d, j, k, m, q, r were separated hot during reflux. Similarly, other compounds (Table 1) were prepared and crystallised from proper solvents

Results and Discussion

The ir spectra of aminomethyl compounds prepared from primary amines (3a-t) exhibited a weak and sharp band at 3450-3420 cm⁻¹ assignable to associated NH group. The ir spectra of all compounds (3a-z) exhibited peaks at 1730-1705s (lactonic carbonyl of coumarin ring system)⁷, 1600-1585 (C-C stretch within aromatic ring), 2950-2880 (C-H of alkyl) and 1390-1175 cm⁻¹ (C-N).

Compound 2 showed $\nu_{\max}$ 2962, 2800, 1720, 1600, 1280, 1090 and $\rho_{\max}$ 650 cm⁻¹; δ (90 MHz, CDCl₃) 4.0 (3H, s, C₈-OCH₃), 4.8 (2H, s, C₅-CH₂Cl), 6.55 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₆-H), 7.0 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₆ or C₇-H), 7.25 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₆ or C₇-H) and 8.0 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₄-H).

The methylene protons attached to C₅ position of 3 (C₅-CH₂-N) exhibit a signal at δ 4.42 (3h) while similar signal is observed at δ 4.8 for 2 (C₅-CH₂-Cl). The low electronegativity of nitrogen atom in comparison to that of chlorine caused

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL[†] DATA OF COMPOUNDS (3)*

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	M.p.** °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
3a	H	C ₆ H ₅	190 ^a	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N
3b	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	197 ^a	71	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N
3c	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	210 ^b	61	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N
3d	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	215 ^b	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N
3e	H	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	184 ^a	72	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₄ N
3f	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	168 ^a	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₄ N
3g	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	183 ^b	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₂ N
3h	H	<i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	204 ^c	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ NCl
3i	H	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	185 ^d	51	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ NCl
3j	H	<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄	205 ^b	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ NBr
3k	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	277-78 ^b	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂
3l	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	265 ^b	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂
3m	H	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	230 ^b	71	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂
3n	H	<i>p</i> -COCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	245 ^b	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂
3o	H	<i>m</i> -COCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	177 ^b	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₄ N
3p	H	<i>p</i> -NH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	305 ^b	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂
3q	H	<i>o</i> -NH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	210 ^e	72	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂
3r	H	β-Naphthyl	218 ^b	55	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂
3s	H	α-Naphthyl	190 ^a	52	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N
3t	H	<i>p</i> -COOC ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	174 ^b	56	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N
3u	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	169 ^a	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₂ N
3v	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	185 ^d	55	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N
3w		Morpholine	110 ^a	55	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ O ₄ N
3x		N-Phenylpiperazine	190 ^a	63	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂
3y		2-Methylpiperidine	115 ^a	60	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₂ N
3z		4-Methylpiperidine	165 ^d	60	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₂ N

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**Crystallisation solvent : ^aAlcohol, ^bDMF+water, ^calcohol+benzene, ^dalcohol+water, chloroform.

[†]3a $\nu_{\max}$ 3 450, 2 950, 1 710, 1 600, 1 270 and 1 180 cm^{-1} ; δ (90 MHz; CF₃COOH) 4.1 (3H, s, C₆-OCH₃), 5.1 (2H, s, C₆-CH₂N), 6.65 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-3), 7.92 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-4) and 7.2-7.65 (m, ArH and NH); 3d $\nu_{\max}$ 3 420, 2 820, 2 950, 1 720, 1 600, 1 280 and 1 190 cm^{-1} ; δ (90 MHz, CDCl₃) 2.1 (3H, s, OCH₃-C₆H₄N), 3.95 (3H, s, C₆-OCH₃), 4.42 (2H, s, C₆-CH₂N), 6.35 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-3), 7.9 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-4) and 6.6-7.2 (m, ArH and NH); 3u $\nu_{\max}$ 2 950, 2 750, 1 720, 1 600, 1 280 and 1 175 cm^{-1} ; δ (90 MHz, CDCl₃) 1.2 (3H, t, NCH₂CH₃), 3.42 (2H, q, NCH₂CH₃), 3.95 (3H, s, C₆-OCH₃), 4.6 (2H, s, C₆-CH₂N), 6.45 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-3), 7.92 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-4) and 6.7-7.3 (m, ArH).

upfield shift of the methylene protons in 3 compared to that in 2. Thus the substitution of aminomethyl group at C₈-position in the coumarin ring system is confirmed by ir and pmr spectra.

Antibacterial activity: Some of the selected compounds 3a, b, e, i, j, r-u, x (Table 1) were tested for their antibacterial activity by cup-plate method⁹ in alcohol-benzene solvent *in vitro* using *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. The standard antibacterial drug used was phthalylsulphathiazole. Compounds 3i and 3r were found active against *S. aureus* (activity, 100 ppm concn.; inhibition zone diameter, 6-8 mm) and 3x was found active against *E. coli* (activity, 100 ppm concn.; inhibition zone diameter, 6-8). Rest of the compounds were found inactive at 100 ppm concentration.

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